

RoboFireFuseNet: Robust Fusion of Visible and Infrared Wildfire Imaging for Real-Time Flame and Smoke Segmentation[★]

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
wildfire
segmentation
multimodal
infrared

ABSTRACT

Concurrent image segmentation of flames and smoke is challenging, as smoke frequently obscures fire in standard RGB imagery, necessitating the use of other spectral bands such as Infrared (IR). Existing multimodal models are either too computationally demanding for real-time deployment or too lightweight to capture fine-grained sparse fire patterns that may escalate into large wildfires. Moreover, they are typically trained and validated on simplistic datasets, such as Corsican or FLAME1, which lack the dense smoke occlusion present in real-world scenarios. We introduce RoboFireFuseNet (RFFNet), a real-time deep neural network that fuses RGB and IR data using attention mechanisms, a detail-preserving decoder, and class-balance training techniques. RFFNet establishes a benchmark on a challenging, realistic wildfire dataset with dense smoke, creating a foundation for practical comparison in future wildfire segmentation research. Despite its lightweight design, it also achieves state-of-the-art results on a general urban benchmark, demonstrating versatility. Its combination of accuracy, real-time performance, and multimodal fusion makes RFFNet well-suited for proactive, robust and accurate wildfire monitoring. Code is available at: <https://gitfront.io/it/dfotiou/eiTd3o9UURjn/RoboFireFuseNet-private>

1. Introduction

Wildfire is an increasing global challenge driven by the effects of climate change [1], both in terms of frequency and destructive power, posing severe threats to human lives [2], the environment, and our economies [3]. Consequently, wildfire imaging, detection, and image segmentation have become critical areas of focus within the scientific community. Wildfire imaging sensors capturing the visible (RGB) or infrared (IR) spectrum can be airborne (using UAVs) and land-based on static or moving platforms. They are beneficial for wildfire management, automating pre-fire monitoring for early detection [4] and providing crucial information during a wildfire to model spread and guide firefighting strategies [5].

Various spectral bands offer distinct advantages for imaging fire. The visible spectrum provides color information but is degraded by smoke [6] that may obscure fire. Short-wave infrared (SWIR) effectively detects high-temperature flames through smoke [7]. Mid-wave infrared (MWIR) is less effective due to absorption by atmospheric CO₂ and H₂O [8]. In contrast, long-wave infrared (LWIR) reliably captures low-temperature thermal emissions in dense smoke [9], making it ideal for detecting smoldering fires in the early stage [10].

The application of multimodal semantic segmentation to wildfire detection faces significant bottleneck, despite

Figure 1: Wildfire image sample from (a) Corsican dataset [15] (b) FLAME1 dataset [16] and (c) RGB, (d) LWIR images from FLAME2 dataset [17].

the success of fusion-based models [11, 12] on benchmark datasets [11, 13]. Current models are often caught in a performance trade-off, being either too resource-intensive for real-time use [12, 14] or insufficiently robust to accurately capture small fire instances [11]. This problem is exacerbated by a prevalent architectural trend in efficient segmentation Deep Neural Networks (DNN): prioritizing speed via aggressive early-layer downsampling. Such a strategy fundamentally limits the model's capacity to perceive small, sparse, irregularly shaped objects, which is essential for identifying the critical, early-stage fire regions that can escalate into large-scale wildfires.

Beyond architectural constraints, existing wildfire-specific DNN semantic segmentation models are mostly trained on overly simplistic datasets, such as Corsican [15] (Fig. 1), where flames are clearly visible, or unrealistic datasets like FLAME1 [16] (Fig. 1b), which depict fires in snowy environments. In these datasets, minimal modality occlusion limits the value of multimodal fusion, and few models segment both flames and smoke. Relying solely on flame detection is often insufficient: flames can be distant, partially hidden, or obscured by smoke, making smoke a crucial signal for early detection. Running separate models for

[★]The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Commission - European Union (under HORIZON EUROPE (HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions) under grant agreement 101093003 (TEMA) HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-01).

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flames and smoke is impractical on resource-limited edge devices like UAVs.

To address the aforementioned challenges, we present RoboFireFuseNet (RFFNet), a real-time multimodal semantic segmentation model for robust flame and smoke segmentation in wildfires. In addition to RGB input, the model utilizes the LWIR spectrum to identify obscured heat signatures and low-temperature early flame spots. RFFNet extends the high-performance PIDNet framework [18] by incorporating independent modality pathways and an attention-enhanced fusion module that captures long-range contextual dependencies while preserving crucial boundary details. A U-Net-style decoder [19] with skip connections retains high-resolution spatial features, enabling precise segmentation. The model is trained on the challenging FLAME2 drone dataset [17] (see Figs. 1c, 1d) using specialized loss functions and data augmentations to mitigate severe class imbalance, establishing RFFNet as a computationally efficient and highly effective solution.

In summary, our novel contributions are as follows:

- We propose a novel, real-time fusion DNN with modality-specific pathways, attention-based fusion for RGB and IR streams and a detail preserving decoder.
- A unified model segments both flames and smoke, addressing severe class imbalance.
- Our method achieves robust and accurate detection of small, obscured flames in a challenging, realistic wildfire dataset.
- RFFNet matches state-of-the-art (SOTA) performance on challenging segmentation benchmarks while being smaller and more computationally efficient.

The remainder of this paper reviews related work in wildfire segmentation (Section 2) and details our proposed RFFNet architecture (Section 3). We then present a comparative analysis against existing methods on segmentation datasets (Section 4) and an ablation study to validate our design choices (Section 5).

2. Related Work

In this section, we review approaches for flame and smoke segmentation using single- or multi-spectrum methods. In the latter, we additionally explore recent fusion segmentation methods applied to general benchmark segmentation datasets, rather than wildfire-specific scenarios.

2.1. Single Spectrum Wildfire Image Segmentation

Deep neural networks (DNN) have recently been extensively applied in the wildfire RGB image region segmentation domain. The YOLOv7 model, when paired with the efficient MobileViTv2 [20] or an augmented Efficient Layer Aggregation Network (ELAN) [21] equipped with an attention module, significantly enhances its receptive field and attention capabilities for flame detection and segmentation tasks.

A combination of the YOLOv5 object detector and the U-Net [19] segmentation model has been used in [22] for flame segmentation tasks. Attention modules and residual blocks were effectively incorporated within a U-Net architecture for the semantic segmentation of smoke in [23]. A lightweight CNN architecture was developed that utilizes depth-wise separable convolution, point-wise group convolution, and a channel shuffling strategy to significantly reduce model size for IoT-assisted transportation systems [24].

Both classical computer vision and DNN models have been proposed to solve flame and smoke segmentation utilizing infrared imagery. In the classical domain, histogram-based IR segmentation has been used to identify hot image regions, which are then combined with optical flow estimation and motion vector analysis to recognize flame-related pixels [25]. Another approach used K-Means clustering for flame image region segmentation, followed by refinement with the Chan-Vese Segmentation Model [26, 27]. On the DNN front, some efforts have focused on maximizing performance in complex scenes. One study [28] implemented an enhanced YOLOv5-seg model [29] incorporating spatial pyramid pooling and a channel attention module, while another proposed a multi-task model based on YOLOv8 that integrates a Kolmogorov-Arnold Network to boost feature extraction [30].

2.2. Multi-spectral Image Fusion for Segmentation

Fusion strategies for multiple image modalities can be categorized as early, intermediate, or late. Early fusion merges raw inputs, which is efficient but risks one modality overshadowing another, causing information loss. Late fusion processes modalities in separate networks and combines final outputs. This is simple but misses cross-modal correlations and scales poorly. Intermediate fusion offers a balance by first extracting modality-specific features before merging them in deeper layers. This preserves essential information while enabling effective cross-modal analysis, making it the preferred approach in most SOTA techniques.

Various multimodal techniques have been developed for wildfire segmentation. Methods range from color space transformations for flame segmentation [31] to more advanced spectral fusion approaches. For instance, encoder-decoder architectures fuse multi-scale RGB and IR features using cross-modal skip connections for flame segmentation [32], while other models process RGB and IR data in parallel pipelines before fusion [33]. Research has also extended beyond dual-spectrum analysis, incorporating six spectral bands via vision transformers for smoke segmentation [34] or developing lightweight four-channel (RGB-IR) models [35] to reduce complexity in scenes with clearly visible wildfires. Despite these advances, no existing multimodal approach simultaneously segments the closely related regions of flame and smoke, particularly on challenging datasets.

Multimodal fusion of RGB and IR images has been explored for general segmentation tasks. MFNet [11] is extremely lightweight model using intermediate fusion but has

Figure 2: RoboFireFuseNet: Proposed RGB-IR image fusion architecture for flame and smoke segmentation. Modality-specific features are processed independently, fused, and refined through a fusion path incorporating semantic, spatial, and boundary cues. Final RGB, IR, and fused features undergo Channel Attention, while the PIDNet Bag [18] module merges detail and semantic paths guided by boundary information. Shortcut links and a U-Net-like decoder enable precise spatial reconstruction.

Figure 3: Channel Attention Module: RGB and IR features are concatenated. Average and Max pooling with an MLP generate channel importance weights are applied to the concatenated features. A CNN then reduces the channel dimension.

limited capacity for complex scenes. RTFNet [12] integrates features at multiple encoder stages. More advanced methods like GMNet [14] and EGFNet [36] utilize multistage fusion and boundary segmentation. To prevent over-reliance on one modality, a common issue on multimodal tasks with multiple target classes, CRM [37] employs complementary masking. Recently, Sigma [38] integrated a selective State Space Model (SSM) with a Siamese Visual Mamba [39] architecture. Despite these advancements, a clear gap persists in the literature, defined by the inherent trade-off between real-time performance and high accuracy (Fig. 7), while wildfire monitoring critically requires both.

3. Proposed Method

3.1. RGB and IR Feature Fusion

The baseline of our model, PIDNet [18], features a contextual path that captures high-level semantic information and a spatial path that focuses on local spatial image detail preservation. This dual-path approach is inspired by concepts explored in [40], where convolutions with different strides are used to effectively capture both spatial and

contextual features. However, segmentation relying solely on these two paths may lead to small region suppression and imprecise region boundary delineation. Proportional-Integral (PI) controllers face similar limitations when handling high-frequency signals. To address these shortcomings, PIDNet [18] introduced a third path dedicated to detecting class boundaries. This path specifically refines the spatial details near object edges and significantly improving boundary precision. This three-path design allows the model to achieve a balanced combination of semantic understanding, spatial detail preservation, and boundary refinement, making it a leading choice for real-time and high-accuracy semantic segmentation tasks.

For accurate fire and smoke segmentation, including small-scale instances, without compromising inference speed or requiring heavy computation, the proposed three-path architecture proves highly effective. We extend this design by incorporating both RGB and IR modalities. To achieve this, we adopt an intermediate fusion strategy in which each modality is first processed independently to extract modality-specific features prior to fusion. Moreover, we duplicate the baseline’s lightweight backbone before the three-path split, assigning one branch to each modality. The extracted features from both spectra are then fused through a channel attention mechanism and subsequently fed into the semantic, detail, and boundary paths (Fig. 4).

To effectively fuse RGB and IR features, we employ a channel attention mechanism that adaptively calibrates channel-wise feature responses. Initially, feature maps from the two modalities are concatenated along the channel dimension, resulting in a combined feature map with $2C$ channels. To aggregate spatial information, both global average pooling and global max pooling are applied in parallel, generating two distinct context descriptors. These descriptors are then processed through a shared weight network consisting of two fully connected (FC) layers in a bottleneck structure: a first FC layer reduces the channel dimensionality, followed by a ReLU activation, and a second FC layer

restores it. The outputs are then merged and passed through a sigmoid function to create the final attention map.

Mathematically, given a concatenated feature map $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 2C}$, the channel attention map $\mathbf{M}_c \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1 \times 2C}$ is computed as:

$$\mathbf{M}_c(\mathbf{F}) = \sigma \left(\mathbf{W}_2 \left(\delta \left(\mathbf{W}_1 \left(\text{AvgPool}(\mathbf{F}) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \mathbf{W}_2 \left(\delta \left(\mathbf{W}_1 \left(\text{MaxPool}(\mathbf{F}) \right) \right) \right),$$

where σ denotes the sigmoid function, δ is the ReLU function, and the weights of the shared FC layers are $\mathbf{W}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{\frac{2C}{r} \times 2C}$ and $\mathbf{W}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{2C \times \frac{2C}{r}}$, with $r = 16$ being the reduction ratio.

The calibrated feature map $\mathbf{F}' \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 2C}$ is obtained by element-wise multiplication:

$$\mathbf{F}' = \mathbf{M}_c(\mathbf{F}) \odot \mathbf{F}$$

where \odot represents element-wise multiplication. Finally, a point-wise convolution is applied to project the calibrated feature map from $2C$ channels down to C channels, producing the final fused output $\mathbf{F}_{\text{fused}} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C}$:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{fused}} = \text{Conv}_{1 \times 1}(\mathbf{F}')$$

This mechanism enables the network to selectively emphasize salient channels from the fused RGB-IR data, resulting in a more robust and discriminative feature representation.

To further preserve unique modality-specific information, each modality also has a dedicated semantic path, similar to the baseline's, which maintains features that might otherwise be suppressed during fusion. Finally, the modality-specific and fused features are fused using channel attention (Fig. 3), but with a higher reduction rate of $r = 32$ for efficiency. This ensures that both shared and unique features contribute effectively to the final segmentation.

3.2. Transformer-Based Semantic Path

Leveraging convolution operations within the encoder backbone efficiently extracts local information from feature images while maintaining high performance and speed. However, using only CNN blocks limits the model's ability to capture long-range dependencies, an important factor in wildfire segmentation, where flame and smoke regions exhibit strong contextual and spatial relationships. The position of one often indicates the position of the other, as shown in results section 5, making it crucial to model these dependencies. To address this, we enhance the semantic path by replacing only two convolution blocks with the second and third transformer blocks from SwinV2 [41]. SwinV2's sliding-window self-attention reduces computational cost while capturing global context across the image. By leveraging SwinV2's long-range dependency modeling [41], our approach improves inter-class interaction and model capacity while keeping complexity low and inference suitable for real-time use. The schematic of the three-pathway fusion module is illustrated in Fig.4.

Figure 4: Fusion module that include three paths—semantic, detail, and boundary and described in PIDNet [18] are enhanced by stages two and three of SwinV2-T (green boxes). The PAG facilitates semantic information injection into the detail path, and PPM enables multi-scale context aggregation via the pyramid pooling module as described in [18].

3.3. Preserving Fine-Grained Spatial Details

The baseline architecture uses the detailed path to recover spatial information lost during downsampling. However, since the detail path itself is downsampled by a factor of four early in the network, this poses a challenge to our task, as small flame regions, which are critical in wildfire scenarios, may be lost. To address this, we incorporate the U-Net-style [19] skip connections. Shortcuts from the early layers are connected to the later layers that are upsampled through interpolation to progressively form the segmentation image map at the spatial dimensions of the original image. This approach ensures that fine-grained spatial details, such as small flame regions, are preserved, leading to more accurate and reliable segmentation of critical areas.

3.4. Addressing Class Imbalance

PIDNet [18] employs a cross-entropy loss function to supervise the intermediate layer of the detail path, the final layer of the semantic path, the boundary features in the semantic path, and the output of the boundary path. RFFNet follows the same supervision structure but replaces the loss for the first two losses with the Lovász-Softmax loss [42]. This modification dynamically addresses the substantial class imbalance among wildfire categories namely background, smoke, and flame, by considering them as regions rather than individual pixels.

The Lovász-Softmax loss directly optimizes the Jaccard index (Intersection over Union, IoU) for each class c . The IoU measures the overlap between the predicted pixel set \mathbf{p}_c and the ground-truth pixel set \mathbf{g}_c :

$$J_c = \frac{|\mathbf{p}_c \cap \mathbf{g}_c|}{|\mathbf{p}_c \cup \mathbf{g}_c|}$$

This approach is particularly effective for handling class imbalance. Unlike standard loss functions that can be dominated by large classes, the Lovász-Softmax loss normalizes the contribution of each class by its size. The per-class loss,

Table 1
Performance Comparison on Wildfire Scenes

Method	BG Recall (%)	BG IoU (%)	Flame Recall (%)	Flame IoU (%)	Smoke Recall (%)	Smoke IoU (%)	Avg Recall (%)	MIoU (%)
PIDNet-RGB [18]	93.51	90.96	52.13	19.54	81.35	71.14	75.66	61.21
PIDNet-IR [18]	86.76	83.68	89.17	47.66	73.21	44.81	83.05	58.71
PIDNet-Early [18]	95.46	93.65	81.59	52.34	84.64	74.1	88.25	73.90
EFSIT* [24]	92.42	89.4	91.18	77.76	86.86	73.12	90.15	80.09
MFNet[11]	95.45	92.68	96.08	65.70	89.06	82.40	93.53	80.26
RTFNet[12]	95.12	76.77	37.36	30.36	89.13	76.25	73.87	65.42
GMNet [14]	88.63	83.65	41.92	15.39	72.04	63.20	67.53	54.08
EGFNet[36]	91.29	88.73	49.59	21.05	81.93	73.16	74.27	60.98
Sigma-T [38]	96.67	93.93	92.54	78.727	88.38	86.12	92.6	86.27
RFFNet (Ours)	98.2	95.08	93.85	81.5	91.08	87.98	94.37	88.17

* denotes reimplementaion with multimodal input (early fusion) and fire/smoke output.

Figure 5: Grad-CAM visualizations of the effect of different layers for flame segmentation: (a) input image, (b) early layer in IR modality path, (c) post-Swin Transformer layer in fusion path, and (d) corresponding layer in the semantic path of the baseline PIDNet-Early fusion model.

$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Lovász},c}$, is scaled by the inverse of the number of ground-truth pixels for that class, $|\mathbf{g}_c|$:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Lovász},c} \sim \frac{1}{|\mathbf{g}_c|} \sum_{i \in \mathbf{g}_c} \ell_i$$

where ℓ_i is the pixel-wise error. This scaling mechanism increases the penalty for misclassifying pixels belonging to smaller classes, as their errors are divided by a smaller denominator. Consequently, the model is forced to learn underrepresented classes more effectively, leading to a more balanced training process.

To further reduce class imbalance and contextual overfitting, we adapted the copy-paste augmentation strategy [43] and we extended it for our multimodal model. The method increases the prevalence of underrepresented fire with respect to smoke instances while simultaneously diversifying their background context. Our extension preserves the integrity of the multimodal signal: when an object is copied, we extract its segmentation mask and the corresponding pixels from both the RGB and the co-registered IR source images. These patches are then pasted into a new background pair at the same spatial location. This process creates a coherent, dual-spectrum sample that forces the model to learn robust, generalizable features of the target classes, independent of their frequency or original environment. A further challenge is the model’s tendency to overfit by associating each segmentation target with a single input modality. Specifically, the model learns to rely predominantly on the RGB input (\mathbf{X}_{RGB}) for detecting smoke and on the infrared input (\mathbf{X}_{IR}) for detecting fire. This strong learned

dependency can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} P(y_{\text{smoke}} | \mathbf{X}_{\text{RGB}}) &\gg P(y_{\text{smoke}} | \mathbf{X}_{\text{IR}}), \\ P(y_{\text{fire}} | \mathbf{X}_{\text{IR}}) &\gg P(y_{\text{fire}} | \mathbf{X}_{\text{RGB}}), \end{aligned}$$

where y_{smoke} and y_{fire} are the respective segmentation labels. Such over-specialization reduces the model’s robustness, as the failure of one modality would impair its ability to detect the associated target. To mitigate this overfitting, we employ modality dropout as a regularization strategy. During each training step, one of the two modalities is randomly set to zero with probability p , forcing the network to learn from the remaining input stream.

4. Experimental Results

4.1. Dataset

The availability of wildfire datasets containing paired RGB and LWIR images is limited, and to our knowledge, none include both flame and smoke region annotations. In our tasks, we utilized the FLAME2 [17] dataset, which provides paired RGB and IR images. We manually annotated the flame and smoke regions, and masks are provided in our code repository. This dataset captures prescribed fires in Arizona, from which 995 synchronized, aligned, and extracted pairs of RGB and LWIR frames were obtained. The resolution used for training and inference was set to 256×256 . Pixels that concurrently contain flame and smoke were classified as flame. The annotations are publicly available in our code repository.

While our main task is wildfire scenarios, in order to evaluate general performance and directly compare with recent fusion strategies, we used the publicly available urban dataset MFNet [11], which includes segmented annotations for nine classes with paired RGB and IR images. We adhered to the authors’ train, validation, and test split scheme. The resolution used for training and inference was set to 480×640 pixels.

4.2. Implementation Details

The evaluation metrics are Intersection over Union (IoU) and Recall, computed per class c .

$$\text{IoU}_c = \frac{|\mathbf{p}_c \cap \mathbf{g}_c|}{|\mathbf{p}_c \cup \mathbf{g}_c|} \quad (1)$$

Figure 6: Qualitative evaluation of flame and smoke segmentation on FLAME2 (a-h) and urban dataset MFNet (i-q).

Figure 7: Comparison of fusion strategies on MFNet dataset mIoU vs. computational speed (FPS) on RTX 4090

$$\text{Recall}_c = \frac{|\mathbf{p}_c \cap \mathbf{g}_c|}{|\mathbf{g}_c|} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{p}_c and \mathbf{g}_c denote predicted and ground-truth pixels, respectively. Recall emphasizes true positive coverage, important for safety-critical tasks.

During training, we augmented the dataset using three categories of transformations. We first applied common geometric operations, namely random scaling, flipping, and cropping. To improve the model’s robustness to varying illumination, we then introduced photometric jittering by randomly altering the brightness, saturation, and contrast of the images. In addition to these pixel-level techniques, we utilized the copy-paste strategy [43], extended to multimodal inputs, to increase the prevalence of underrepresented classes by pasting them into novel object-background compositions.

We utilized the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 1×10^{-3} , weight decay of 5×10^{-5} , and a cosine scheduler featuring a 20-epoch warm-up period, for a total of 500 epochs. Early training stopping was employed when the loss function plateaued. The PIDNet component and the SwinV2 transformer blocks were pre-trained on ImageNet-1K to leverage transfer learning and accelerate convergence. To prevent overfitting and balance modality contributions, we randomly drop the RGB, IR, or fusion path during training with probability $p = 0.3$, promoting robustness and

symmetric learning from both modalities. All experiments were conducted on an NVIDIA RTX 4090 24GB GPU.

4.3. Wildfire Segmentation

In this section, we evaluate the accuracy of RFFNet for simultaneous flame and smoke segmentation, a task not yet addressed on challenging datasets. For comparison, we train the baseline PIDNet with single-source inputs and a standard early fusion model with concatenation of RGB and IR inputs. Although no existing multimodal segmentation model targets both fire and smoke, we reimplement a recent model for wildfire segmentation, adapting it for multimodal fusion with early fusion and dual outputs for fire and smoke segmentation. Additionally, we reproduce several fusion architectures and train them on our wildfire segmentation task.

As far as the performance of baseline PIDnet, the RGB single input model achieves a higher mIoU than the IR one, and early fusion significantly outperforms both, as illustrated in Tab. 1. As expected, the RGB modality performs better in detecting smoke, while infrared excels in identifying flames. PIDnet [18] early fusion achieves a high mIoU compared to other fusion strategies, demonstrating that it serves as an effective baseline for our problem.

As demonstrated in Tab. 1, our proposed RFFNet surpasses alternative fusion strategies across nearly all metrics and classes. The most significant challenge remains the segmentation of flames, which are often obscured by dense smoke or appear as small, sparse regions (Fig. 6). RFFNet effectively addresses this by leveraging skip connections, which yield a notable improvement in recall and mIoU for the flame class. While models like MFNet [11] and EFSIT [24] that also exploit skip connections, achieve competitive recall, their lower IoU scores indicate imprecise segmentation, likely due to their shallower architectures failing to capture deep semantic information. In contrast, although the Sigma-T model [38] delivers strong results, its superior performance comes at the cost of being 1.5 times larger and significantly slower during inference, highlighting the efficiency of our approach.

Table 2

Performance Comparison on the MFNet Dataset

Method	mIoU (%)	Avg Recall (%)	Params (M)
PIDNet-m RGB [18]	51.52	65.59	34.4
PIDNet-m IR [18]	50.70	65.27	34.4
PIDNet-m Early [18]	52.62	69.59	34.4
MFNet [11]	39.7	59.1	0.73
Sigma-T [38]	60.23	71.3	48.3
EGFNet [36]	54.8	72.7	62.5
CRM-T [37]	59.7	-	59.1
GMNet [14]	57.3	74.1	153
RTFNet [12]	53.2	63.08	185.24
RFFNet (Ours)	60.6	71.1	29.5

4.4. Urban Dataset Segmentation

In addition to wildfire scenarios, we evaluate the model’s performance on the urban dataset, MFNet [11]. This evaluates the model’s capability in general segmentation tasks beyond wildfire-specific challenges. Its performance is compared with other real-time models, as shown in 2.

RFFNet requires significantly fewer parameters than most methods, addressing a gap in the development of real-time, compact fusion models. As illustrated in Fig. 7a, our model strikes an excellent balance between accuracy and inference speed, achieving the highest mIoU while being much faster than competitors. While larger variants of CRM [37] and Sigma [38] report slightly higher mIoU scores, their substantial parameter counts make them unsuitable for direct comparison with our efficiency-focused approach. Our model achieves a new state-of-the-art (SOTA) IoU of 44.28% on the challenging guardrail class, outperforming the closest competitors, CRM [37] and Sigma [38], by over 20% (Fig. 6). This is attributed to three key factors: shortcut connections preserving spatial details, copy-paste augmentation improving generalization for rare objects, and the Lovász-Softmax loss effectively handling class imbalance. Furthermore, baseline results in Table 2 show that on the urban dataset, simple early fusion of RGB and IR provides only a modest 1% mIoU improvement. This contrasts with the significant gains seen in wildfire scenarios, suggesting that the value of RGB-IR fusion is context-dependent and most critical in challenging conditions like smoke, where the modalities are highly complementary.

5. Ablation study

We present the architectural and training strategies used to develop a robust segmentation framework for multimodal fusion, specifically designed for wildfire scenarios. Our contributions enhance RFFNet’s real-time processing while significantly improving smoke and flame segmentation from RGB and IR images. Table 3 shows the performance drop for each class when any proposed RFFNet addition is omitted, underscoring the effectiveness of our approach.

The most significant improvement resulted from the RFFNet decoder. As previously mentioned, the early reduction of spatial dimensions improves computational efficiency but considerably impairs the model’s ability to

Table 3

Component Impact (Metric: IoU)

Component	Smoke	Flame	MIoU
w/o U-Net-like Decoder	85.18 (-2.8)	67.5 (-14)	82.57 (-5.6)
w/o Lovász-Softmax Loss	85.88 (-2.1)	77.0 (-4.5)	85.37 (-2.8)
w/o Modality Paths	87.63 (-0.35)	78.7 (-2.8)	87.15 (-1.02)
w/o SwinV2 Blocks	87.28 (-0.7)	80.0 (-1.5)	87.27 (-0.9)
w/o Copy-paste Augmentation	87.83 (-0.15)	80.8 (-0.7)	87.87 (-0.3)
Proposed Model	87.98	81.5	88.17

accurately segment small objects, such as flame segments in Figs. 6a-6h and guardrails (purple color) in Figs. 6i-6q. Figure 5b shows that the model can achieve high spatial precision in segmenting flame instances even in the early layers. Therefore, propagating this data to the later layers is essential for accurate spatial reconstruction and information retrieval.

The second most impactful improvement was the introduction of the Lovász-Softmax loss function instead of vanilla cross-entropy, which effectively addressed the issue of class imbalance. The inclusion of modality paths provided a boost, particularly for the segmentation of the flame class.

Although the SwinV2 blocks and copy-paste augmentation did not result in substantial gains in segmentation accuracy, they played a pivotal role in enhancing the generalization and the interpretability of the fusion model. As shown in Fig. 5c, after the transformer, the entire region beneath dense smoke becomes activated. This suggests that, within the fusion process, the smoke, being the most dominant class, can propagate information about the underlying position of the flame. In contrast, as seen in Fig. 5d, the corresponding activation map from the PIDNet’s CNN layer does not highlight any significant indication of the underlying flame within the smoke region. This indicates that the transformer allows for interactions between the features of the classes.

6. Conclusion

In this work we introduced a novel, real-time segmentation model that closes the performance gap between computationally intensive, state-of-the-art architectures and less accurate, lightweight alternatives. Specifically designed for the challenging task of concurrent smoke and flame segmentation, our model’s effectiveness stems from a synergistic architecture that leverages multimodal RGB and Infrared (IR) inputs via an intermediate-fusion strategy that incorporates attention mechanism, a decoder that preserve high-frequency spatial details for precise boundary delineation, and tailored loss and augmentation techniques to overcome severe target class and modality imbalance. Our experiments not only demonstrate high performance in wildfire segmentation but also prove that its core principles are successfully transferable to other complex multimodal segmentation problems with small and rare objects, notably in urban scene analysis, suggesting a broad applicability of the proposed architecture.

References

- [1] S. E. Garroussi, F. D. Giuseppe, C. Barnard, F. Wetterhall, Europe faces up to tenfold increase in extreme fires in a warming climate, *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science* (2024).
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:267359783>
- [2] G. Chen, Y. Guo, X. Yue, S. Tong, A. Gasparrini, M. L. B. et al., Mortality risk attributable to wildfire-related pm2.5 pollution: a global time series study in 749 locations., *The Lancet. Planetary health* 5 9 (2021) e579–e587.
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:237485837>
- [3] S. Stefanidis, V. Alexandridis, V. Spalević, R. L. Mincato, Critical success factors of small and medium wildfire effects on soil erosion dynamics: The case of 2021 megafires in greece, *The Journal "Agriculture and Forestry"* (2022).
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:251087781>
- [4] A. Bouguettaya, H. Zarzour, A. M. Taberkit, A. Kechida, A review on early wildfire detection from unmanned aerial vehicles using deep learning-based computer vision algorithms, *Signal Process.* 190 (2021) 108309.
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:239659928>
- [5] F. Huot, R. L. Hu, N. Goyal, T. Sankar, M. Ihme, Y.-F. Chen, Next day wildfire spread: A machine learning dataset to predict wildfire spreading from remote-sensing data, *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 60 (2022) 1–13.
- [6] G. Wang, H. Li, S. Ye, H. Zhao, H. Ding, S. Xie, Rfwnet: A multi-scale remote sensing forest wildfire detection network with digital twinning, adaptive spatial aggregation, and dynamic sparse features, *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* (2024).
- [7] G. Mazzeo, A. Falconieri, C. Filizzola, N. Genzano, N. Pergola, F. Marchese, Wildfire detection and mapping by satellite with an enhanced configuration of the normalized hotspot indices: results from sentinel-2 and landsat 8/9 data integration, *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* (2025).
- [8] S. Shah, T. Grübler, L. Krempel, S. Ernst, F. Mauracher, S. Contractor, Real-time wildfire detection from space—a trade-off between sensor quality, physical limitations and payload size, *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* 42 (2019) 209–213.
- [9] J. A. Sobrino, F. Del Frate, M. Drusch, J. C. Jiménez-Muñoz, P. Manunta, A. Regan, Review of thermal infrared applications and requirements for future high-resolution sensors, *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 54 (5) (2016) 2963–2972.
- [10] C. D. Elvidge, M. N. Zhizhin, M. N. Zhizhin, F.-C. Hsu, K. E. Baugh, M. R. Khomarudin, Y. Vetruta, P. Sofan, Suwarsono, D. Hilman, Long-wave infrared identification of smoldering peat fires in indonesia with nighttime landsat data, *Environmental Research Letters* 10 (2015).
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:154795749>
- [11] Q. Ha, K. Watanabe, T. Karasawa, Y. Ushiku, T. Harada, Mfnet: Towards real-time semantic segmentation for autonomous vehicles with multi-spectral scenes, in: 2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), IEEE, 2017, pp. 5108–5115.
- [12] Y. Sun, W. Zuo, M. Liu, Rfnet: Rgb-thermal fusion network for semantic segmentation of urban scenes, *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 4 (3) (2019) 2576–2583.
- [13] S. S. Shivakumar, N. Rodrigues, A. Zhou, I. D. Miller, V. Kumar, C. J. Taylor, Pst900: Rgb-thermal calibration, dataset and segmentation network, in: 2020 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation (ICRA), IEEE, 2020, pp. 9441–9447.
- [14] W. Zhou, J. Liu, J. Lei, L. Yu, J.-N. Hwang, Gmnet: Graded-feature multilabel-learning network for rgb-thermal urban scene semantic segmentation, *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing* 30 (2021) 7790–7802.
- [15] T. Toulouse, L. Rossi, A. Campana, T. Celik, M. A. Akhloufi, Computer vision for wildfire research: An evolving image dataset for processing and analysis, *Fire Safety Journal* 92 (2017) 188–194.
- [16] A. Shamsoshoara, F. Afghah, A. Razi, L. Zheng, P. Z. Fulé, E. Blasch, Aerial imagery pile burn detection using deep learning: The flame dataset, *Computer Networks* 193 (2021) 108001.
- [17] X. Chen, B. Hopkins, H. Wang, L. O’Neill, F. Afghah, A. Razi, P. Fulé, J. L. Coen, E. M. Rowell, A. C. Watts, Wildland fire detection and monitoring using a drone-collected rgb/ir image dataset, 2022 IEEE Applied Imagery Pattern Recognition Workshop (AIPR) (2022) 1–4.
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:253659545>
- [18] J. Xu, Z. Xiong, S. P. Bhattacharyya, Pidnet: A real-time semantic segmentation network inspired by pid controllers, in: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, 2023, pp. 19529–19539.
- [19] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, T. Brox, U-net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation, in: Medical image computing and computer-assisted intervention—MICCAI 2015: 18th international conference, Munich, Germany, October 5–9, 2015, proceedings, part III 18, Springer, 2015, pp. 234–241.
- [20] S. Mehta, M. Rastegari, Separable self-attention for mobile vision transformers, *ArXiv abs/2206.02680* (2022).
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:249394941>
- [21] X. Cao, Y. Su, X. Geng, Y. Wang, Yolo-sf: Yolo for fire segmentation detection, *IEEE Access* (2023).
- [22] W. S. Mseddi, R. Ghali, M. Jmal, R. Attia, Fire detection and segmentation using yolov5 and u-net, in: 2021 29th European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO), IEEE, 2021, pp. 741–745.
- [23] Z. Wang, P. Yang, H. Liang, C. Zheng, J. Yin, Y. Tian, W. Cui, Semantic segmentation and analysis on sensitive parameters of forest fire smoke using smoke-unet and landsat-8 imagery, *Remote Sensing* 14 (1) (2021) 45.
- [24] K. Muhammad, H. Ullah, S. Khan, M. Hijji, J. Lloret, Efficient fire segmentation for internet-of-things-assisted intelligent transportation systems, *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* (2022).
- [25] C. Yuan, Z. Liu, Y. Zhang, Fire detection using infrared images for uav-based forest fire surveillance, 2017 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS) (2017) 567–572.
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:45783060>
- [26] B. Yang, H. Pan, S. He, K. Han, X. Zhao, Forest fire thermal infrared image segmentation based on k-v model*, 2021 IEEE 24th International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work in Design (CSCWD) (2021) 1275–1280.
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:235235474>
- [27] T. Chan, L. Vese, An active contour model without edges, in: International conference on scale-space theories in computer vision, Springer, 1999, pp. 141–151.
- [28] K. Niu, C. Wang, J. Xu, C. Yang, X. Zhou, X. Yang, An improved yolov5s-seg detection and segmentation model for the accurate identification of forest fires based on uav infrared image, *Remote. Sens.* 15 (2023) 4694.
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:263210050>
- [29] G. Jocher, A. Chaurasia, A. Stoken, J. Borovec, NanoCode012, Y. Kwon, et al., ultralytics/yolov5: v7.0 - YOLOv5 SOTA Realtime Instance Segmentation (Nov. 2022). doi:10.5281/zenodo.7347926.
URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7347926>
- [30] C. Chen, Y. Liu, C. Zhang, J. Li, X. Chen, An efficient multi-task forest fire and smoke detection model, *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* 160 (2025) 111958.
- [31] X. Xie, J. Wang, Y. Zhang, J. Xin, L. Mu, X. Xue, A uav forest fire detection method based on dual-light vision images, in: 2023 CAA Symposium on Fault Detection, Supervision and Safety for Technical Processes (SAFEPROCESS), IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [32] S. Guo, B. Hu, R. Huang, Real-time flame segmentation based on rgb-thermal fusion, in: 2021 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics (ROBIO), IEEE, 2021, pp. 1435–1440.
- [33] X. Rui, Z. Li, X. Zhang, Z. Li, W. Song, A rgb-thermal based adaptive modality learning network for day–night wildfire identification, *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation* 125 (2023) 103554.

- [34] J. Liu, J. Li, S. Peters, L. Zhao, A transformer boosted unet for smoke segmentation in complex backgrounds in multispectral landsat imagery, *ArXiv abs/2406.13105* (2024).
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:270619426>
- [35] J. Yu, Q. Chen, A lightweight four-channel multi-modal model to improve computational performance of automated fire detection, *Journal of Safety Science and Resilience* (2025) 100254.
- [36] S. Dong, W. Zhou, C. Xu, W. Yan, Egfnets: Edge-aware guidance fusion network for rgb–thermal urban scene parsing, *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* (2023).
- [37] U. Shin, K. Lee, I. S. Kweon, J. Oh, Complementary random masking for rgb-thermal semantic segmentation, in: *2024 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 11110–11117.
- [38] Z. Wan, P. Zhang, Y. Wang, S. Yong, S. Stepputtis, K. Sycara, Y. Xie, Sigma: Siamese mamba network for multi-modal semantic segmentation, *arXiv preprint arXiv:2404.04256* (2024).
- [39] L. Zhu, B. Liao, Q. Zhang, X. Wang, W. Liu, X. Wang, Vision mamba: Efficient visual representation learning with bidirectional state space model, *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.09417* (2024).
- [40] C. Yu, J. Wang, C. Peng, C. Gao, G. Yu, N. Sang, Bisenet: Bilateral segmentation network for real-time semantic segmentation, in: *Proceedings of the European conference on computer vision (ECCV)*, 2018, pp. 325–341.
- [41] Z. Liu, H. Hu, Y. Lin, Z. Yao, Z. Xie, Y. Wei, J. Ning, Y. Cao, Z. Zhang, L. Dong, et al., Swin transformer v2: Scaling up capacity and resolution, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2022, pp. 12009–12019.
- [42] M. Berman, A. R. Triki, M. B. Blaschko, The lovász-softmax loss: A tractable surrogate for the optimization of the intersection-over-union measure in neural networks, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2018, pp. 4413–4421.
- [43] G. Ghiasi, Y. Cui, A. Srinivas, R. Qian, T.-Y. Lin, E. D. Cubuk, Q. V. Le, B. Zoph, Simple copy-paste is a strong data augmentation method for instance segmentation, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2021, pp. 2918–2928.